

Polarographic Studies on the Effect of Various Experimental Conditions on the Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction of Eu(III)

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The polarographic behaviour of Eu(III) under various experimental conditions of temperature, concentration and nature of supporting electrolytes, aqueous organic solvents, and ionic and non-ionic surfactants, has been studied quantitatively in terms of the values of kinetic parameters. The electro-reduction of Eu(III) has been found to be diffusion-controlled in each case.

THE polarographic behaviour of Eu(III) has been studied in various supporting electrolytes and complexing media by several workers¹⁻¹⁰. Besides, many¹¹⁻¹⁸ have undertaken polarographic studies on the composition and stability of Eu(III) complexes with formate, acetate, salicylate, citrate, tartrate, lactate, benzoate and amino acids as ligands. So far as the nature of the polarographic reduction of Eu(III)→Eu(II) is concerned there has been divergence in results from one system to another. In some cases the one-electron reduction process of Eu(III) has been reported to be reversible while in others it has been found to be quasi-reversible or even irreversible. It is in this background that the present study, dealing with the effect of various experimental conditions, viz., the change in temperature, the change in concentration and nature of different supporting electrolytes, the presence of aqueous mixtures of organic solvents, and the presence of ionic and non-ionic surfactants, on the electrode reaction of Eu(III) has been undertaken.

Experimental

Chemicals were used of reagent grade. A stock solution (0.025 M) of Eu₂O₃ (Sigma, U.S.A.) was prepared in the minimum amount of perchloric acid and diluted with double distilled water. The depolarizer concentration was kept at $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in each solution. Sodium perchlorate (0.1 M) was used as a supporting electrolyte. As no maximum was encountered in any of the experimental conditions, addition of any suppressor was avoided. The polarograms of the solutions were taken by a manual set up²⁸⁻³⁰. Corrections for iR drop were applied wherever found necessary. The dme had the following capillary characteristics: $m = 2.83$ mg/sec; $t = 3.28$ sec; $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.44$ mg^{2/3}sec^{-1/6}; $h_{corr} = 71.83$ cm (in 0.1M NaClO₄, open circuit).

The number of electrons, n , involved in the electro-reduction of Eu(III) was determined by

millicoulometric method¹⁹ and was found to be one. Knowing the value of n , the diffusion coefficient, D , of Eu(III) was calculated by Ilkovic equation. Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop (i.e. the maximum current) was recorded.

Results and Discussion

Eu(III) gives a single well-defined and diffusion-controlled cathodic wave under different experimental conditions. The slope values of log plots are greater than the theoretical value expected for one-electron reduction process. The value of α was obtained from the relation $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4} = \frac{0.0564}{\alpha n}$ (at 25°) where n is the total number of electrons involved in the electrode reaction. The value of $(E_{3/4} - E_{1/4})$ was obtained from C-V curves of Eu(III) under the following experimental conditions: (i) at different temperatures, ranging from 25 to 55°, (ii) at different concentrations (0.05-1.0 M) of supporting electrolytes viz., KCl, KNO₃, NaCl, NaClO₄, NH₄Cl, Ba(NO₃)₂, Mg(NO₃)₂, Al(NO₃)₃, HClO₄ and H₂SO₄, (iii) at different percentage of aqueous mixtures of organic solvents such as methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, formamide, dimethylformamide and propylene carbonate and (iv) presence of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants such as laurylpyridinium chloride (LPC), cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC), sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), dodecyl benzene sulphonate (DBS) and Triton X-100.

It was found that the value of α was greater than 0.5 under all experimental conditions except in the presence of increasing concentrations (1×10^{-3} - $8 \times 10^{-3}\%$) of LPC and at higher percentages ($\geq 4 \times 10^{-3}$) of Triton X-100 where the value of α was found to be less than 0.5. Thus it has been ascertained²⁰ that under the above experimental conditions the electrode reaction of Eu(III) is quasi-reversible

except in the presence of LPC and at higher concentrations ($\geq 4 \times 10^{-3}\%$) of Triton X-100 when the electrode reaction of Eu(III) becomes totally irreversible. The kinetic parameters (α and $k_{s,h}$) of the quasi-reversible electrode reaction of Eu(III) have been determined by Gellings' method²¹. In the cases where the electrode reaction of Eu(III) becomes irreversible, the kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) have been determined by Koutecky's method²²⁻²⁵.

The values of kinetic parameters (α and $k_{s,h}$) increase (from 0.69 to 0.58 and 5.0×10^{-3} to 8.3×10^{-3} cm/sec, respectively) with rising temperature (25-55°) thereby showing that the electrode reaction of Eu(III) tends towards reversibility. In other words, the rate of electron-transfer from dme to the depolarizer is facilitated by a rise in temperature. This is also borne out by a positive shift in

$E_{1/2}$ with the rise in temperature. The behaviour of the electrode reaction of Eu(III) at increasing temperatures is in harmony with the view of Brdicka²⁶ who put forward that a positive shift in $E_{1/2}$ at elevated temperatures is indicative of easier reduction and an increased degree of reversibility of an electrode process.

A decrease in α and $k_{s,h}$ values is noted with increasing concentrations of supporting electrolytes (salts or acids) (Table 1), percentage of organic solvents (Table 2) and various surfactants (Table 3). This indicates that the electrode reaction of Eu(III) is tending from quasi-reversible nature towards irreversibility. The effect of supporting electrolytes may be attributed to the increased adsorption of the ions of the supporting electrolytes on the electrode surface at higher concentrations²⁷.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS (α AND $k_{s,h}$) FOR THE QUASI-REVERSIBLE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Eu(III) IN PRESENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTES

[Supporting electrolyte] M	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /sec	α	$k_{s,h} \times 10^4$ cm/sec
KCl						
0.20	10.2	0.680	75	8.8	0.79	5.0
1.00	10.0	0.690	100	8.5	0.59	1.9
KNO ₃						
0.20	10.9	0.675	80	10.0	0.74	5.4
1.00	11.1	0.680	95	10.4	0.62	3.8
NaCl						
0.20	10.8	0.685	80	9.9	0.74	2.4
0.50	10.0	0.695	100	8.5	0.59	1.8
NaNO ₃						
0.20	9.9	0.650	80	8.2	0.74	3.6
1.00	10.4	0.653	95	9.1	0.62	2.3
NaClO ₄						
0.20	10.2	0.670	90	8.8	0.66	4.0
1.00	10.4	0.673	95	9.1	0.62	3.9
NH ₄ Cl						
0.20	10.2	0.680	85	8.8	0.69	1.5
1.00	11.6	0.700	100	11.3	0.59	0.7
Ba(NO ₃) ₂						
0.10	11.2	0.670	90	10.7	0.66	2.4
0.20	9.9	0.675	100	8.2	0.59	1.8
Mg(NO ₃) ₂						
0.20	9.1	0.700	105	7.1	0.59	1.9
1.00	9.1	0.705	107	7.1	0.58	1.8
Al(NO ₃) ₃						
0.20	10.2	0.675	102	8.8	0.59	2.1
1.00	7.7	0.705	110	5.0	0.54	1.1
HClO ₄						
0.10	10.9	0.680	94	10.0	0.63	2.8
0.20	11.7	0.710	100	11.5	0.59	2.1
H ₂ SO ₄						
0.20	10.2	0.760	80	8.8	0.74	10.3
1.00	9.6	0.830	90	7.6	0.66	9.7

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS (α AND $k_{s,h}$) FOR THE QUASI-REVERSIBLE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Eu(III) IN PRESENCE OF AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF DIFFERENT ORGANIC SOLVENTS

[Organic solvent] % v/v	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /sec	α	$k_{s,h} \times 10^4$ cm/sec
0	11.4	0.660	70	11.0	0.84	4.6
Methanol						
10	9.5	0.670	72	7.6	0.84	3.5
50	8.1	0.730	80	5.5	0.74	2.3
Ethanol						
25	7.7	0.730	80	5.1	0.79	4.6
50	6.0	0.790	85	3.0	0.71	4.1
Acetonitrile						
10	10.4	0.665	75	9.1	0.79	6.1
25	10.5	0.760	80	9.4	0.74	3.1
Formamide						
10	9.9	0.680	82	8.2	0.72	4.1
25	9.4	0.710	85	7.5	0.69	3.9
50	8.5	0.740	90	6.1	0.64	2.8
Dimethylformamide						
25	7.92	0.710	78	5.3	0.76	3.4
50	5.81	0.735	78	2.8	0.74	3.1
75	8.10	0.810	80	2.2	0.73	1.4
Propylene carbonate						
4	10.5	0.750	95	9.4	0.62	3.7
15	8.8	0.860	100	6.5	0.60	2.7

Taking different sets of supporting electrolytes such that the anion remained the same when the cation was varied and vice-versa, the effect of anions and cations constituting the supporting electrolytes at a certain concentration (0.2 M) on the value of the $k_{s,h}$ has been attempted. The order of $k_{s,h}$ values is as follows :

(i) for univalent cations (as nitrates) : $K^+ > Na^+ > Al^{3+} > Mg^{2+} > Ba^{2+}$;

(ii) for anions (as sodium salts) : $ClO_4^- > NO_3^- > Cl^-$.

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS (α AND $k_{s,h}$) FOR THE QUASI-REVERSIBLE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Eu(III) IN PRESENCE OF SOME IONIC AND NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS

[Surfactant]	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ cm^2/sec	α	$k_{s,h} \times 10^3$ cm/sec
CPC						
1.0×10^{-3}	11.1	0.640	80	10.4	0.78	7.2
1.2×10^{-3}	9.7	0.650	85	7.9	0.69	2.4
DBS						
1.0×10^{-3}	10.4	0.670	75	9.1	0.79	3.8
1.0×10^{-3}	9.7	0.685	90	7.9	0.64	1.8
SLS						
1.0×10^{-3}	10.5	0.640	60	9.4	0.98	7.4
4.0×10^{-3}	10.3	0.655	80	8.9	0.74	2.5
Triton X-100						
1.0×10^{-3}	10.2	0.700	82	8.8	0.72	2.4
4.0×10^{-3}	9.7	0.760	115	7.9	+0.47	* 7.4×10^{-9}
8.0×10^{-3}	9.6	0.785	116	7.7	+0.46	* 5.1×10^{-9}
LPC						
1.0×10^{-3}	10.6	0.740	110	9.5	+0.49	* 7.0×10^{-7}
8.0×10^{-3}	9.8	0.810	152	8.2	+0.35	* 6.9×10^{-9}

+ denotes the value of α_{na}

* denotes the value of $k_{f,h}$

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